

LLRM: A Robust Approach for Defending Large Language Models Against Prompt Injection Attacks

Amin Rezanejad¹, Mobin Mehrpour¹, Yasaman Boreshban^{2*}

¹.Computer Engineering Department, University of Guilan, Rasht, Iran.

².Computer Engineering Department, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) have inspired a lively field of applications due to their remarkable adeptness in understanding and generating natural language. However, while leveraging the emerging opportunities of their broad appeal across various services, it is crucial to address the new and unknown threats in this domain. According to the OWASP Foundation, Prompt Injection attacks are ranked as the foremost risk related to large language models. Despite recent studies in this field, no comprehensive approach has yet been established to fully harness the potential of LLMs while mitigating vulnerabilities and threats. In this study, we analyze the complexities and consequences of Prompt Injection Cyber Attacks in both standalone LLMs and programs integrated with LLMs. Furthermore, we propose an approach to enhance the security of chatbots based on LLMs by monitoring threats and predicting attacks. The proposed approach demonstrated robust performance in two implementations. In the first implementation, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 91%, and in the second implementation, an accuracy of 99% was obtained. These results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed method in accurately detecting and mitigating threats even under challenging conditions. This research will inspire further investigations to develop stronger defenses against critical threats such as Prompt Injection attacks, paving the way for a more secure era of large language models.

Keywords: Large Language Models, Natural Language Processing, Prompt Injection Attack, AI Security, Software Security.

1 - Introduction

The emergence and prosperity of artificial intelligence, just like other digital technologies, has brought with it unique and unique capacities in creating tremendous transformations and profound changes. People rely on the Internet to access the information they need, and the advanced capabilities of language processing tools have greatly increased interactions with computers [1]. In recent years, the adoption of Large Language Models (LLMs) across diverse applications has grown substantially [2]. We are in the amazing age of artificial intelligence with a rapid movement towards the smartness of many different things in life. However, it is worth noting that with every step forward, we are accompanied by new and unknown threats just as new and emerging opportunities dawn. Therefore, in order to benefit to the maximum from the advantages of automation and improve functions with intelligence in various fields, it is necessary to try to control and reduce the risks that are lurking in artificial intelligence systems. Prompt Injection

Corresponding Author: Yasaman Boreshban
E-Mail: yas.boreshban@gmail.com

Attacks are one such threat where hackers try to trigger AI chatbot applications into unauthorized conversations. Prompt injection attacks are inspired by traditional injection attacks such as SQL injection [3, 4, 5] and XSS attacks [6, 7, 8].

After this introduction, in the second part of the article, the definition of Large Language Models and the exchange of information with them are discussed. In the third part, we examine security threats and hacker attacks of the Prompt Injection type in independent LLMs and programs integrated with LLMs. In the fourth section, we will present the approach of Large Language Robust Models (LLRMs) to improve security and robustness with the aim of detecting and preventing Prompt Injection Attacks in web applications such as artificial intelligence chatbots. And at the end, we will discuss the contents of the article and suggestions for future research in order to develop the approach of large language resistance models to researchers and engineers in the fields of software and artificial intelligence.

2 - The Large Language Models

Natural language processing (NLP) is a field of artificial intelligence and linguistics that deals with the understanding, interpretation and production of human languages by computer systems. Natural language processing was created to facilitate the user's work and to satisfy the desire to communicate with the computer in natural language [9]. Large Language Models (LLMs) are advanced artificial intelligence models that use deep learning techniques such as Transformer and are trained on large sets of textual data. Transformer architecture, which was introduced in 2017 [10], has been one of the most successful models in natural language processing. For example, BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) is one application of Transformer that has improved the accuracies of previous models on a large number of language processing tasks.

Research shows that Transformer-based natural language processing (NLP) models have achieved advanced performance for name entity recognition, relation extraction, sentence similarity, natural language inference, and question answering [11]. Also, in 2020, a new model named Reformer has been introduced by Google, which is much more efficient than Transformer in terms of speed and memory [12]. Large Language Models (LLMs), such as GPT-3, PALM, LLaMA, and GPT-4, and products built on them, such as ChatGPT, have recently attracted a lot of attention [13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Many attentions from journalists [18, 19, 20], policy makers [21, 22, 23] and researchers in many fields [24, 25, 26, 27] are expanding. Large language models (LLMs) consistently show significant performance on various tasks [28, 29, 30]. Especially in the field of software engineering, recently a group of researchers from Brown University and several Chinese universities showed that ChatGPT artificial intelligence chatbot can develop software in about seven minutes for less than one dollar [31].

3 - Background and Related Works

From the point of view of the OWASP³ Foundation, which plays a special role in huge projects to improve software security and secure the web, it recently published a report on the vulnerability of Large Language Models and ranked Prompt Injection Attacks as the number one threat⁴. Also on August 30, 2023, the National Cyber Security Center (NCSC) in England has

³Open Web Application Security Project

⁴<https://owasp.org/www-project-top-10-for-large-language-model-applications/>

highlighted the concern that AI chatbots based on Large Language Models are easily induced to perform malicious tasks and businesses should be cautious⁵. Prompt Injection Attacks have emerged as a significant challenge for the growing field of artificial intelligence applications, posing substantial risks. This issue becomes even more critical when AI chatbots are integrated into various applications, as both the frequency and impact of these attacks are likely to increase. Consequently, ensuring the security of Large Language Models is paramount. Unfortunately, addressing the problem of Prompt Injection Attacks is extraordinarily difficult.

Generative models heavily rely on the prompts provided in the input [32]. When interacting with Large Language Models such as Chat-GPT, users submit their request in the form of a question, sentence, or short paragraph. It is worth noting that the given request is very important in providing the output produced by the model, so that it specifies the desired information or the expected response of the users. Therefore, AI chatbots respond based on user input. Therefore, attackers can influence the result by using some phrases in the text of the command and tricking the chatbots. For example, an AI-based chatbot used by an online store's website may be infected with a Prompt Injection during a Conversation and Prompted to perform an unauthorized transaction. Now, according to the security level of the website, the level of vulnerability and the depth of penetration of the attack will give the cyber attacker the power to control the artificial intelligence agent and will have serious consequences such as the disclosure of important information and the implementation of malicious actions, which can potentially be very be dangerous.

so chatbots that work based on big language models are tricked by speaking. In the Prompt Injection Attack, with carefully designed and directed commands, the model is provoked to change its main behavior and encourage to perform unauthorized reactions. Prompt Injection is a new hacking technique for Large Language Models that enables attackers to change the behavior of the model and see the output as desired. Today, the use of artificial intelligence chatbots in various government applications, banking, education, shopping, tourism, medicine and other services is expanding. And yet, as connections increase, vulnerabilities will become more common. An easy and common way to check the readiness and operation of the Prompt Injection Attack independently and separately from the integration with an application service is to interact directly with the Open-AI chatbot as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Abnormal Chat-GPT response to a user Prompt.

⁵<https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/blog-post/chatgpt-and-large-language-models-whats-the-risk>

However, in this case, at a superficial glance the effect of the Prompt Injection seems relatively harmless, since the attacker only caused the bot to display an unusual response in the output. But with a deeper look, it becomes clear that we are facing a dangerous and security vulnerability, and it should be noted that this seemingly simple case is considered a green light for hackers to infiltrate and act with wrong intentions.

And on the other hand, and more importantly, it warns artificial intelligence researchers about the need to look at security, and software development engineers must be on the lookout for improving and increasing security in order to integrate Large Language Models into various application services. In the following, we will examine a more detailed example of Prompt Injection to encourage the popular Chat-GPT chatbot to write a phishing email in Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Figure 2. In the first step, the request to write the text of the phishing email is given and we are faced with a negative response from the chatbot.

Figure 3. In the second step, an enticing prompt about the characteristics of the phishing email is used to get the chatbot to change its behavior.

Figure 4. In the third step, considering the persuasion to change the behavior, the request to write the text of the phishing email is given again.

Figure 5. And in the final step, it can be seen that complete instructions are provided for how to set up the structure of a phishing email, and now, in the first step, the chatbot was not willing to accept and respond.

In Figures 2, 3, 4, and 5, we have shown a simple example of potential vulnerabilities. Cases of highlighting and exposing similar vulnerabilities have motivated the movement and departure of companies such as Open-AI to deal with vulnerabilities. Also, in order to double the importance and attention to the security of large language models, it is worth mentioning that the vulnerabilities of Bing (Copilot) and Blender chatbots have been revealed for prominent companies Microsoft and Meta, respectively, in the tests of engineers and researchers. In the following, related work on the security and robustness of large language models has been proposed in recent research.

Yan et al. [33] introduced the virtual Prompt injection (VPI) method, in which malicious processes are injected into the training, without changing the original model. This method bypasses the conventional defense mechanism and emphasizes security in the design of models. Gershak et al. [34] showed that indirect Prompt injections can induce models to perform activities outside the original scope and even malicious, such as phishing and spreading malware. These types of targets are harder to detect because of the integration of malicious inputs into normal conversations. Liu et al. [35] analyzed solutions to counter these threats, including the use of secure input techniques and more secure integration methods for LLM-based payment systems. Also, Salem et al. [36] introduced the Maatphor tool, which is able to detect and distinguish malicious requests from normal requests. In addition to the Prompt Injection scheme, Piet et al. [37] have investigated rapid injection (rapid injection) and categorized them into static, semi-dynamic, and dynamic types. Several countermeasure strategies have been proposed to reduce the vulnerability of the models.

More recent research such as Ghasemlou et al. [38] have also developed methods to improve the performance of models through multi-objective generation, which, in addition to increasing the robustness, also enhances the generation of models in managing security threats. Overall, recent and ongoing studies emphasize the critical need for advanced security measures, robust input sanitization, and improved integration practices to protect LLM from hostile exploitation.

4 - The Approach of Large Language Robust Models (LLRMs)

Due to the novelty of this cyber threat, researchers have not conducted extensive studies in this field. Therefore, considering the originality of the subject under study, in the current research, we provide an opening and a strong foundation for future research and practical applications, which will contribute to the goal of achieving sustainable cyber security in the era of artificial intelligence. In these models, the border between data and instructions is blurred, which is very important from the point of view of cyber security. The inability to separate user input instructions from the data to be processed is the reason for modeling models and changing their behavior. These attacks rely on the inability to separate received requests and processed data [39]. This is one of the main reasons for parameter injection attacks and changing the behavior of models. Figure 6 is presented as a fishbone diagram to analyze this problem. This diagram, which is based on Thinking and Experience, visually displays the main causes and sub-causes of the inability to separate data from processing instructions and emphasizes the importance of secure design and implementation of monitoring processes.

Figure 6. Analyzing the Causes of Prompt Injection Attacks in Large Language Models and Artificial Intelligence Chatbots

Therefore, to protect Large Language Models against Prompt Injection Attacks, distinguishing between instructions and data is a fundamental solution. Our proposed approach is to analyze the sentiment of the input instruction with the help of the language models themselves. That is, in the first place, the sense of the input command should be analyzed and then, if it is normal and non-destructive, it should be delivered to the extensive knowledge of the language model for processing and responding. To clearly state the proposed idea of integrating a fine-tuned language model with a dataset of Prompt Injection Attack in the input of the chatbot to analyze the sentiment and detect maliciousness for filtering and otherwise send it for processing with the data and extensive knowledge of the chatbot artificial intelligence. This approach can be used as an additional layer for security and separation of data and instructions. We call the defense approach based on the language models themselves Large Language Robust Models (LLRMs), which can effectively help to deal with Prompt Injection attacks for sentiment analysis and intent detection as an additional layer of security. By combining fine-tuned language models with a dataset of Prompt Injection Attacks to preprocess and filter inputs, this approach not only increases system security, but also improves the robustness of the Large Language Model and Accuracy of Chatbot Responses. In the following, the implementation steps of the proposed approach are explained and shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. The Large Language Robust Models (LLRMs)

The Large Language Robust Model (LLRM) Approach Consists of Two Layers: a Control Language Model to Counter the Prompt Injection Attack and a Main Language Model to Respond to the Prompt.

The chatbot receives user input. A primitive language model such as BERT fine-tuned with a dataset of Prompt Injection Attacks also analyzes the input in terms of sentiment and other aspects such as the intent of the input (whether the input contains malicious or unusual commands). Based on sentiment and intent analysis, input is divided into two categories: normal input and suspicious input. Normal inputs are directed to the large language model to process and provide a response. And if the input looks suspicious, we will filter and send an error message. From a guess based on science and experience, the advantages of the large language resistance model approach can be increased security, improved

accuracy of answers, and generalization ability. Due to the fact that malicious inputs are detected and filtered before reaching the main system, the security of the system increases significantly. Also, the system can increase the accuracy of its answers. Because it filters out malicious entries and processes only valid and correct entries, and we will improve the user experience by reducing incorrect or irrelevant answers. In addition, the fine-tuned language model can be used to detect different types of Prompt Injection Attacks and has the ability to generalize in different situations and scenarios.

Among the possible disadvantages, adding an additional layer for filtering and analyzing messages can increase the processing time and delay the response of the system. And probably, the design and implementation of a filtering system based on the language model will require high implementation complexities and technical resources. Sentiment analysis and user intent detection may not always be accurate and errors may occur in detecting malicious or non-malicious inputs. that we need to continuously use and train new data in order to maintain the accuracy at the best level.

Accurate analysis and detection of user's feelings and intentions is one of the important challenges in implementing this approach. Human emotions are complex and can be expressed in many ways. Also, to train and optimize linguistic models, large and diverse data is needed, which includes malicious and non-destructive messages. Attackers are constantly changing their methods to bypass security systems. This makes language models need to be constantly updated. And these will be one of the most important possible challenges facing our proposed approach.

5 - Implementing the Control Layer

The BERT language model can be fine-tuned for various natural language processing tasks[40] and has been a huge success in the field[41]. In this implementation of the LLRM approach, the BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representation of Transformers) model was chosen for the defense and control layer as an ideal solution for detecting rapid injection attacks. Given its exceptional capabilities in natural language processing, BERT can accurately capture context and complex semantic relationships between words. Unlike one-way models, BERT uses two-way approach to encoding information, enabling it to analyze text simultaneously from both directions (left-to-right and right-to-left). This feature allows BERT to deeply understand the exact context of sentences and model the semantic relationships between words with high accuracy. Since rapid injection attacks usually involve manipulating user inputs and changing the instructions or data processed by the model, BERT's ability to detect anomalies and unusual patterns in the input makes it particularly effective for this task. In addition, as a pre-trained model, BERT can be quickly trained on domain-specific attack data, enabling it to effectively distinguish between malicious and malicious inputs.

In implementing and fine-tuning the BERT model, we used the Prompt Injection dataset available in Hugging Face, which included both Normal and Malicious commands. It is worth noting that since the dataset was small, we also used the cross-validation method. In addition, for reliability, we prepared a larger dataset than Hugging Face, although with some modifications to this dataset, such as balancing the number of normal and malicious commands, to avoid bias and bias in order to implement the principles of fine-tuning. BERT model and improve the results. The datasets used included two columns of input Prompts and Labels: normal (0) and injection (1). As we said, we did a separate implementation for each dataset. The small dataset had 662 rows, of which 546 rows were for the main and 116 rows were for the test. The distribution of the main and test section labels is shown in Figure 8. But the larger dataset, after preparation and cleaning according to our study and implementation needs, was used to fine-tune the BERT language model for the addition of a defense layer for detecting normal input Prompts and Injection. We introduce it in this study and it is available in the link along with the implementations⁶. For this dataset, we had 6970 rows, which we divided into 40 for the original set, 30 for the valid set, and 30 for the test set. The division percentage and the distribution of labels can be seen in Figure 9.

Figure 8. A) Train Set label Distribution, B) Test Set label Distribution

⁶ <https://github.com/aminrezanejad20/LLRMs>

Figure 9. A) Distribution of Train and Test labels, B) Distribution of Train and Test labels

In the first implementation, we tuned the BERT model on a smaller dataset. Due to the smaller dataset, we used the scaffolded cross-validation method with k-fold=5. The model achieved an overall accuracy of 91%. For detecting malicious commands (Class 1), the precision was 100%, recall was 83%, and the F1-score was 91%. For normal commands (Class 0), the precision, recall, and F1-score were 85%, 100%, and 92%, respectively. The macro-average F1-score across both classes was 91%, indicating balanced performance in detecting both normal and malicious commands. The weighted-average precision, recall, and F1-score were 93%, 91%, and 91%, respectively, reflecting the overall robustness of the model. The results and provide more reliable performance. These findings highlight the robustness of the approach and show strong performance in accurately classifying inputs even with smaller datasets, which confirms the robustness and effectiveness of the approach.

And in the second implementation, we tuned the model for 1 epoch (to avoid overfitting) with a batch size of 16 and a learning rate of 2e-5. In this implementation, the model achieved an overall accuracy of 99%. For the detection of negative commands, the precision was 98%, recall was 99%, and the F1-score was 99%. For the detection of positive commands, the precision was 99%, recall was 98%, and the F1-score was 98%. The macro-average F1-score and weighted-average F1-score were both 99%, reflecting a balanced and robust performance across both classes. These results highlight the significant potential of using BERT as a control layer in the Large Language Robust Model (LLRM) approach to mitigate rapid injection attacks. The confusion matrix is also presented in Figure 12 for both implementations.

Figure 12. A) Confusion Matrix for Implementation 1, B) Confusion Matrix for Implementation 2

The results of the evaluations are summarized in Table 1. It is worth noting that the model inference time in our tests was about 0.09 seconds. The results are promising for the effectiveness of the LLRM approach.

Table 1. Evaluation Results of Fine-tuned BERT Language Model

Fine-tune the BERT language model					
	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Implementation 1	Normal (0)	0.85	1.00	0.92	0.91
	Injection (1)	1.00	0.83	0.91	
Implementation 2	Normal (0)	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99
	Injection (1)	0.99	0.98	0.98	

6- Conclusion

This study has highlighted some of the pioneering moves in the realm of improving the security of large language models. The integration approach of a fine-tuned large language model for sentiment analysis and input intent detection; It will be an advanced technique against complex threats. The insights obtained from this study can provide a promising ground for future studies and discoveries. In the end, we end the article with this thought, with the increasing dependence on chatbots and artificial intelligence systems in various fields, including customer service, health, education and business, the need for more effective security mechanisms is felt more. To prevent these threats, it is essential to adhere to security principles in design, continuously test the system, and implement monitoring and limiting tools. The development of innovative approaches to detect and counter attacks, including the use of sentiment analysis and input intent detection, can serve as a turning point in increasing the security and reliability of these systems. We hope our proposed idea will inspire further research to develop stronger Defenses against Prompt Injection Attacks. This is just a basic Approach, it is actually a guess based on science and experience. Future research could lead to solutions and implementations from this approach.

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